

1 **Stage-specific function of Ezh2 in hematopoietic cell type specification from HSC.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the hematopoietic stem cell and in each of the major erythroid, myeloid
8 and lymphoid lineages to discover novel factors associated with blood cell specification in humans. We
9 describe here stage specific activation of Ezh2, observed during lineage commitment from the HSC in
10 multiple cell types. We present evidence indicating mobilization of PRC2 function is accompanied by,
11 perhaps paradigmatically, simultaneous activation of the Xist RNP complex, including KH-domain proteins
12 KHDRBS1 and KHDRBS2 in a developmental sequence aimed at maintaining the precise, dynamic quality
13 of cell-type specification.

14 Citations

15 1. Shen, X., Liu, Y., Hsu, Y.J., Fujiwara, Y., Kim, J., Mao, X., Yuan, G.C. and Orkin, S.H., 2008. EZH1
16 mediates methylation on histone H3 lysine 27 and complements EZH2 in maintaining stem cell identity
17 and executing pluripotency. *Molecular cell*, 32(4), pp.491-502.

18 2. Kamminga, L.M., Bystrykh, L.V., de Boer, A., Houwer, S., Douma, J., Weersing, E., Dontje, B. and
19 de Haan, G., 2006. The Polycomb group gene Ezh2 prevents hematopoietic stem cell exhaustion. *Blood*,
20 107(5), pp.2170-2179.

21 3. Margueron, R., Li, G., Sarma, K., Blais, A., Zavadil, J., Woodcock, C.L., Dynlacht, B.D. and
22 Reinberg, D., 2008. Ezh1 and Ezh2 maintain repressive chromatin through different mechanisms.
23 *Molecular cell*, 32(4), pp.503-518.
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